

CULTUROLOGY

SOCIOCULTURAL INTERACTION BETWEEN THE USER AND THE LIBRARY: NEW TASKS, APPROACHES, FIELDS OF WORK OF UKRAINIAN LIBRARIES

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Abstract

The library as a social and cultural institution develops and transforms adequately to the challenges that arise in the process of historical development. The ideologically tendentious culture-into-masses work of libraries in the past has now transformed into sociocultural activity aimed at the formation of a socially active creative personality. The introduction of interactive forms of library work creates conditions for the effective use of technological opportunities for informatization of the communication domain and contributes to the formation of civil society.

Keywords: library, sociocultural space, cultural self-fulfillment, social media, public communication, sociocultural activity, self-identification.

Libraries, which historically played a leading role in the accumulation and preservation of knowledge and providing access to information, have traditionally carried out educational work, ensured the continuity of generations and performed an important function of popularizing the cultural heritage of humankind as the basis for the formation and development of the sociocultural space. State-of-the-art technological and social changes keep scientific research on the transformation of the cultural and educational function of libraries up to date; clarifying the role of interactive forms of interaction in the user-library system; presenting modern trends in the use of information technology in the sociocultural activities of libraries.

This issue has been reflected in a number of scientific studies. M. Zakirov devoted his work to studying the directions of evolution of library activity as a factor of the modern socio-communication process [1]. The paper identifies priority areas of transformation of library activity, which have already found practical implementation to some extent. In particular, the creation of sociocultural centers of the amalgamated territorial communities on the basis of libraries, expanded representation of libraries on social media, as well as the creation of a digital library on the basis of digitization of existing library funds. O. Hudzenko-Aleksandruk [2] studies the sociocultural space as an environment and factor of self-identification of an individual. The author notes that self-identification of an individual, which happens within the corresponding cultural and linguistic tradition, is one of the forms of human creativity, through which self-awareness, the search for social purpose, and self-establishment take place as an advantage in the competitive struggle with other subjects operating in a certain sociocultural space. O. Kuzmenko and V. Zahumenna devoted their paper to expanding the ideas about the role of libraries and their influence on the development of the up-to-date information society [6]. The authors emphasize that the active dissemination of the experience of library transformation is facilitated by the search for new methods and forms of sociocultural activity of libraries in Ukraine. Modern libraries transform and develop together with society, taking on the role of information, cultural, educational,

social and public centers. N. Zakharova [4] studies the sociocultural activities of the V.I. Vernadsky National Library of Ukraine in the first decades of Ukraine's independence in the context of changes of the forms and methods of library work against the background of informatization of society. The author noted that sociocultural activities reflect the level of development, quality and effectiveness of the library's external and internal communication activities and affect the popularization of key areas of work. The presented analysis of the papers indicates the relevance, multidimensionality and complexity of the issue of transforming library activities, which, in turn, serves as confirmation of the need to continue scientific research.

At the same time, we need a separate study to identify the characteristic features of new forms and approaches to the organization of sociocultural activities of Ukrainian libraries in the modern sociocultural space, which is the purpose of this paper. The paper uses a complex of general scientific research methods: system, comparative, classification, retrospective analysis to determine the key characteristics, features and directions of evolution of library activities in the conditions of sociopolitical transformations.

As A. Koretska emphasizes in her study, "... the basis of the sociocultural space is culture (individual, national, universal) as a set of human achievements. The unifying factors and regulatory mechanisms in this issue are language, cultural and historical traditions, customs, rituals, morality, religion, politics, law, which create the national nature of the sociocultural space. Through the prism of these values, a person realizes the surrounding reality, which is not limited to one national culture, but appears as a holistic system, the foundation of which is universal human values" [2, p. 134]. Libraries as all-in-one repositories that have appropriate means and methods of preserving, classifying, searching, processing and providing information are simultaneously the discoverers of this space for a person and guides in it.

At the same time, the library itself, due to the cultural development of humanity, occupies an important place in the sociocultural space. As a social and cultural

institution, the library quite naturally actively participates in the social and cultural life of a society that develops and transforms adequately to the challenges that arise in the process of historical development, provides people with the necessary knowledge, introduces them to moral guidelines, offers already known and time-tested options for action, and thereby participates in the formation of the sociocultural space.

Meanwhile, the library itself is evolving together with society, the state and the information and communication domain. The socioeconomic problems that Ukrainian society faced in the first decades of independence significantly affected the place and role of libraries in ensuring the cultural leisure of the population and the ability of libraries to conduct effective educational activities. The reduction in funding has had a painful impact on the ability of libraries to replenish their collections with literary novelties and periodicals in a timely and sufficient volume, especially the most popular and sought-after publications. In response to the development of telecommunication technology and the creation of the Internet, there has been a certain re-orientation of the audience towards visual means of leisure. Taken together, these factors have prompted changes in approaches to the organization of library activities.

In particular, in recent decades, an important section of library activity has undergone significant changes, which in Soviet times had a leading ideological function and was implemented in the form of culture-into-masses work inherent in totalitarian societies. It was mostly aimed at ideologically colored mass education, in the process of which the active role belonged exclusively to the organizers of events and invited speakers. The audience was considered an object of influence, and the process itself usually did not involve the active participation of visitors, or was limited to questions and discussions, which ultimately led the participants to a generally acceptable conclusion prepared in advance and ideologically verified by the organizers.

However, the processes of democratization of political life and the establishment of civil society in Ukraine contributed to the formation of awareness of one's own subjectivity, the need to be an active participant in events and an effective person in the mechanisms of vertical and horizontal social communication among a significant part of the population. In these conditions, the transformation of traditional culture-into-masses work into a new form - sociocultural activity of libraries takes place. The majority of library specialists and researchers consider the new form of educational library activity as a logical component of the modern stage of development of the field of social communication, which reflects the quality changes that have occurred in information exchange technology and in sociopolitical relations in general.

Regarding libraries, L. Beilis suggests to interpret this type of social communication as a purposeful system of actions and measures that "should contribute to the improvement of the intellectual, material, and aesthetic-spiritual state of society by bringing to the consciousness of specific users, different in composition

and scope of social groups, scientific knowledge, empirical facts, aesthetic, and moral-ethical values concentrated in library document collections. This is a purposeful process of involving a person in the cultural values of society, specially organized by the library as a social institution" [1, p. 8].

At the same time, it should be emphasized that the process of inclusion indicated by the researcher is considered precisely as an activity aimed at the active role of a person as a co-participant in the process and the creator of a certain cultural product in the form of communicative practice, participation in the organization and holding of workshops, preparation and delivery of presentations, etc. The interactive nature of public communications of a democratic society and social networks such as LiveJournal, Facebook, Instagram, etc., required the abandonment of organizing cultural and educational events in the form of broadcasting appropriately composed information to a certain audience and its passive perception of information. Today's users, who have already gained experience in civic and information subjectivity, needed new forms of interaction with the library. Thus, democratic transformations, combined with mass informatization, led to the transformation of the traditional culture-into-masses work of libraries.

The key component of the new form of relations between users and the library is sociocultural interaction, which, along with the assimilation by the audience of the cultural heritage acquired by their predecessors, also involves mutual influence aimed at a certain spiritual evolution of all participants in the process. Thus, the library complements its function as a relay of knowledge and cultural values with the function of creating new forms of communication, and the users, who take an active part in these communications, find for themselves a new form of cultural self-fulfillment. It is worth noting that this form of organization of sociocultural activity will contribute to the creation of an atmosphere of effective development of the "user-library" system, since it is in interaction that existing problems are better revealed, which, in turn, encourage the development of the system as a whole.

According to O. Kuzmenko and V. Zahumenna, "today it is necessary to rethink the model of building communication between the library and the user, the reader's involvement in the formation and management of the quality of services. Users can help change the library together, make it the most attractive, because they know best what they expect from the library today; users and life itself can suggest what should be changed" [6, p. 27]. In turn, the library will create an important basis for self-improvement and development, and the readers, who saw how the library has changed in accordance with their request, receive additional confirmation of their own subjectivity, will feel a connection with the library and responsibility for its development in the future. As a result, the mutual influence of the user and the library will be organically included in the process of sociocultural activity of the library as a factor in the formation of a socially active personality and its most effective socialization.

Modern and effective sociocultural activities of libraries create conditions for the development of a person's sociality, his/her self-identification as part of a certain social community, united by common cultural and political values, which in turn is an important basis for building a modern democratic and independent state.

According to A. Kurhuzov, "a person's sociocultural self-identification can be defined as a manifestation of an individual's activity in the course of activities aimed at satisfying his/her value-based, cognitive, economic and spiritual needs through self-reference and self-representation as a subject of a certain sector of the sociocultural space. The process of self-identification as a way of gaining support and preserving identity, that is, the correspondence of a certain system of signs that allow an individual to be classified as some type of people, as some social group, is based, on the one hand, on social control over the implementation of the expectations of the environment, and on the other – on the personal basic qualities of the individual, which make possible a certain type of his/her activity, behavior, lifestyle" [7]. Therefore, in current situation, sociocultural activity is aimed not only at familiarizing oneself with socially acceptable models of human behavior, but also at expanding the boundaries of habitual forms of human activity, opening the way to one's spiritual development, and forming a constructive and creative social surroundings as a favorable environment for the most effective self-knowledge and self-development of the individual.

It should be noted that libraries are of key importance in this process. Reflecting on the logic of the development of the process of sociocultural self-identification of an individual in the sociocultural space, A. Kurhuzov noted that "self-identification of an individual occurs within the corresponding cultural and linguistic tradition that has developed in a certain society and at the same time goes beyond this society into the global sociocultural space thanks to the language embodied in information that represents and communicates a multitude of values, norms, role and behavioral guidelines that significantly influence this process" [2, p. 137].

On this entire path of self-identification of the individual, the library can and should walk alongside a person, since it is it that is able to make a person familiar with the cultural and linguistic tradition that has developed in society on a professional level, providing access to the best examples of literature of a particular people. In addition, it is the library, as a repository of documents that record the achievements of civilization, examples and values of national and global culture, that opens a window to a person into the global sociocultural space.

Along with economic and sociopolitical factors, an important motivating factor in the state-of-the-art evolution of the sociocultural activities of libraries is the informatization of the communication field. The explosive growth of information volumes significantly outstrips the human ability to adequately perceive it, changing the usual algorithms for searching and select-

ing data and their critical analysis. Under such conditions, the library, along with the traditional provision of access to cultural heritage, must actively implement new methods of work aimed at developing users' media literacy, information consumption culture, compliance with information security requirements and personal data protection.

According to O. Kuzmenko and V. Zahumenna, "the digital environment makes the activities of libraries more dynamic, accessible to a significant number of users, both real and potential, and opens up opportunities for further development. It has led to the emergence of new functions in the activities of modern libraries. Now they must also be navigators of network resources, content managers, website editors, consultants on working on social networks, organizers of interactive communication, advocacy specialists, etc." [6, p. 28].

The commercialization of the communication domain, a significant expansion of the possibilities and accessibility of network tools for obtaining information for the average person requires the expansion of the use of modern methods of self-presentation of libraries. According to N. Zakharova, library advertising is of particular importance in sociocultural activities. Recently, the level of preparation of advertising and information products has been increasing, in particular invitations, press releases and catalogs. New computer technology is being actively used: Internet forums, advertising on social networks (Facebook), advertising on information electronic screens for readers, guests and employees; Internet presentations (of book exhibitions); electronic calendar of memorable dates [4, p. 198].

Along with this, the increased efficiency of sociocultural activities of libraries will be facilitated by the expanded use of social media and the active representation of libraries there with a focus on interactivity, which meets the needs and already formed behavioral patterns of contemporary social networks users. The information and communication model of library representation on social media, proposed by V. Strunhar, provides not only informing, which is usual for static websites, but also continuous communication with users. The researcher notes that "... we consider library representation on social media as a communicative space in which the implementation of various communicative strategies and practices is possible. It is important to emphasize communication, taking into account interactivity as a constitutive feature of social media. The proposed model makes it possible to trace the relationships between its elements, to find out the impact of the development (or lack thereof) of any one of them on the rest, and to identify directions for increasing the effectiveness of the library's use of social media" [8, p. 297].

Therefore, the representation of libraries on social media allows to fully realize new opportunities of socio-cultural activities of libraries, to satisfy users' request for interactivity and to provide effective feedback in the "user-library" system. It should also be added that the availability of feedback allows responding promptly to users' requests, adjusting the content and nature of information presentation in order to increase

the expected efficiency and qualitative results of the library's sociocultural activities in general.

The next direction of the newest forms of organizing library activities according to the characteristics of interactivity is connected with the previous one and allows significantly expanding the possibilities of sociocultural activities towards organizing the participation of the active part of society in the qualitative filling of the sociocultural space. It is based on the use of the idea of crowdsourcing – involving users in the performance of certain tasks on a volunteer basis. The leaders in the use of crowdsourcing methods among foreign libraries have accumulated considerable experience in involving volunteers in the formation of digital image collections, digitization of historical documents, etc. Thus, “... libraries will not only perform an important task, but will also involve users in joint, socially significant work, thereby contributing to the formation of a civil society falling back on a socially responsible person” [1, p. 34].

Informatization of the communication domain also played an important role in overcoming the challenges that arose in connection with the COVID-19 pandemic and full-scale Russian aggression in Ukraine. In the context of the introduction of quarantine, attention was shifted to the organization of sociocultural activities of libraries in a remote form, which continued during the introduction of martial law. As N. Zakharova and T. Sereda note, “special attention was paid to such relevant forms of sociocultural library activity under the conditions of remote operation as virtual exhibitions, which became an important form of popularization of the rich universal fund of the V.I. Vernadsky National Library of Ukraine in war conditions. After all, exhibitions is one of the main areas of sociocultural communication, which are divided into book and documentary and art exhibitions by the type of exhibits. Most book and documentary exhibitions are thematic displays that highlight modernity, are timed to commemorate significant events, memorable dates, and mark international and state holidays” [5, p. 117]. In today's difficult conditions, thanks to the use of state-of-the-art technological means of communication, libraries have maintained contact with the user, continued to provide information services and conduct sociocultural activities as a significant component of the consolidation of society. Libraries that continue their work alongside other public and state institutions contribute to the stability of society, provide a sense of the steadfastness of the state, and demonstrate the effectiveness of national resistance.

Conclusions. The library as a social and cultural institution naturally and actively participates in the social and cultural life of a developing and transforming society in response to the challenges that arise in the process of historical development. Libraries have appropriate means and methods of preserving, classifying, searching, processing and providing information, and are an active part of the sociocultural space, capable of effectively influencing the quality and nature of its evolution. Due to sociopolitical and economic changes of recent decades, the ideologically tendentious culture-into-masses work of libraries has been

transformed into sociocultural activity aimed at the formation of a socially active creative personality. The sociocultural work of a modern library is aimed at involving each individual in the creation of universal cultural values. The library complements its function as a relay of knowledge and cultural values with the function of creating new forms of communication, and users who take an active part in these communications find for themselves a new form of cultural self-fulfillment. The introduction of interactive forms of sociocultural activity of libraries creates conditions for the effective use of technological opportunities for informatization of the communication domain, contributes to the formation of a civil society falling back on a socially responsible person. The representation of libraries on social media significantly expands the possibilities of self-presentation of library activities, provides effective feedback in the “user-library” system, and opens the way to the development and improvement of new, constructive forms of public communication.

Ukrainian libraries responded quickly enough to the challenges associated with the COVID-19 pandemic and the war. Using state-of-the-art means of communication, readers were continued to be served, access to information resources was maintained, work was launched to form up-to-date databases, and sociocultural activities were continued, in particular, in the form of virtual exhibitions and various online events, presentations of libraries on social networks, etc. In this context, a promising direction for further research is to study the practical experience of sociocultural activities of libraries in difficult sociopolitical conditions.

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